

Data Fusion: Calculation of Feasible Correlations

Chris Moriarity
Takoma Park, MD 20912 USA

Abstract

I have described a method (2001, 2003, 2004, 2009, 2010) for merging two independent samples using data fusion (also known as statistical matching). One sample contains (X,Z) and the other contains (X,Y) , both drawn from a common nonsingular normal (X,Y,Z) distribution. Following Kadane (1978) and Rubin (1986), I employ regression in my approach. I assess the uncertainty introduced during the merge that is due to the unobserved (Y,Z) relationship by repetition over a range of (Y,Z) values that are consistent with the observed data. An essential part of my algorithm is to add random residuals to the regression estimates. My initial approach for estimating the residual variance could fail (be negative) because it used subtraction of estimates from both files. An innovation due to Raessler and Kiesl (2009) give improved results for estimating the residual variance, solving one of the two open problems in the paradigm. The remaining open problem was determining the area of feasible correlations between Y and Z when both Y and Z are multivariate. Building on the foundation described by Kiesl and Raessler (2006), the solution to this problem is now known.

Key Words: Statistical Matching

1. Introduction

I provide a brief introduction to data fusion (also known as statistical matching) in this section. The statistical matching book by D'Orazio, et al. (2006a) is a comprehensive reference, and is recommended reading for anyone who wishes to know more about the subject.

Suppose there are two sample files, File A and File B, taken from two different surveys. Suppose further that File A contains variables (X,Y) , while File B contains variables (X,Z) . X , Y , and/or Z may be vectors. The objective of data fusion is to combine the information in these two files to obtain at least one synthetic file containing variables (X,Y,Z) .

In contrast to record linkage (also known as exact matching), the two files to be combined are not assumed to have records for the same entities. In data fusion the files are assumed to have little or no overlap; hence, records for similar entities are combined, rather than records for the same entities. For example, one may choose to match individuals who are similar on characteristics like gender, age, poverty status, health status, etc.

All statistical matches described in the historic literature have used the X variables that appear in both files as part of the matching process. To illustrate with a simple example, suppose File A has 3 records with X, Y values:

$(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), (x_3, y_3)$, where x_1, y_1 , etc. are specific values of X, Y ,

while File B has 4 records with X, Z values:

$(x_1, z_1), (x_3, z_3), (x_4, z_4), (x_5, z_5)$, where x_1, z_1 , etc. are specific values of X, Z .

In this example, x_1 and x_3 are given values of X , and they appear in both files. x_2, x_4 , and x_5 are given values of X that appear only in one file.

If only the X variables are used to define matches, this is akin to assuming that Y and Z are uncorrelated, given X ; if the variables have normal distributions, then the assumption is that Y and

Z are conditionally independent, given X. This "conditional independence" assumption has been discussed extensively in the data fusion literature (e.g., Rodgers (1984), and references given therein). It has been shown (e.g., Moriarity and Scheuren (2001a)) that the "conditional independence" value of the covariance of (Y,Z) is just one of many possible values that are consistent with the observed data. Assuming conditional independence can lead to final synthetic files with very different distributions than final synthetic files created with other assumed, feasible values of the covariance of (Y,Z).

Given the assumption of conditional independence, one could merge (match) the records with identical values of X to create:

$(x_1, y_1, z_1), (x_3, y_3, z_3)$.

Notice that matching on the given values of x_1 and x_3 (where X is, say, age) does not imply that the (y_1, z_1) and (y_3, z_3) paired data came from the same entities in the population.

What to do with the remaining records is less clear and techniques vary. Broadly, the various strategies employed for statistical matching can be grouped into two general categories: "constrained" and "unconstrained." Each is described in turn.

Constrained matching requires the use of all records in the two files, and thus it preserves the marginal Y and Z distributions. In the above example, for a constrained match one would have to end up with a combined file that also had additional records that used the remaining unmatched File A record (x_2, y_2) and the two unmatched File B records (x_4, z_4) and (x_5, z_5) . In other words, all of the records on both files get used. Notice that, as would generally be the case, one could not limit the role of X in the matching so as to require identical values of X to allow a match; in at least some cases, matches would have to be allowed where X's were close (similar) to one another.

Unconstrained matching does not have the requirement that all records are used. Referring to the above example, one might stop after creating (x_1, y_1, z_1) and (x_3, y_3, z_3) . Usually in an unconstrained match, though, all the records from one of the files (say, File A) would be used (matched) to "similar" records on the second file. Some of the records on the second file may be employed more than once, or not at all. Hence, in the unconstrained case, the remaining unmatched record on File A, the observation (x_2, y_2) , would be matched to make the combined record $(x_2, y_2, z_?)$. The observations (x_4, z_4) and (x_5, z_5) from File B might or might not be included.

A number of practical issues, not discussed in this brief overview, often need to be addressed in data fusion; for example, alignment of universes (i.e., the sums of the weights in the data files should be equal) and alignment of units of analysis (i.e., individual records represent the same units, e.g., persons).

Rodgers (1984) includes a more detailed example of combining two files, using both constrained and unconstrained matching, than the brief sketch provided here. We encourage the interested reader to consult that reference for an illustration of how sample weights are used in the matching process, etc.

Some more recent literature (e.g., Raessler (2002)) includes examples of data fusion where an actual match (a "statistical match") of the data files does not occur. For this reason, we have decided that the terminology "data fusion" is preferable to "statistical matching", because it is more general.

2. The Use of Regression in Data Fusion

Regression-based data fusion was described in Kadane (1978) and Rubin (1986). Moriarity and Scheuren (2001a, 2001b, 2003a, 2003b, 2004) described innovations and extensions of the methods described by Kadane and Rubin, Kadane's method in particular.

Kadane (1978) described a model for data fusion. One model assumption was that the variables in the sample files had a multivariate normal distribution. He pointed out that this model was not universal; sample files could contain variables that were binary, variables that took integer values only, etc. The data fusion literature contains a number of contributions that consider these situations, e.g., D'Orazio, et al. (2006b). Clearly, regression-based data fusion is not always the most appropriate method to apply. Given the current state of development of regression-based data fusion, alternatives should be considered anytime the sample files contain data that do not appear to have a multivariate normal distribution, and it is not feasible to apply transformations to the data to obtain something reasonably close to a multivariate normal distribution.

Kadane's use of regression was to produce estimates of the "missing" values in the sample files: for File A, containing (X,Y), the "missing" value to be estimated was Z; for File B, containing (X,Z), the "missing" value to be estimated was Y. In order to produce these estimates, Kadane needed to make some assumption about the (Y,Z) relationship, and he correctly noted that a number of different assumptions about the (Y,Z) relationship were consistent with the observed data. He emphasized the necessity for exploring a range of assumptions about the (Y,Z) relationship. His emphasis of this necessity was the genesis of the paradigm of assessing the uncertainty in data fusion.

Kadane's model, with some minor changes and innovations, has been shown to be a sound theoretical framework when the variables in the sample files have a multivariate normal distribution (Moriarity and Scheuren (2001a)). Thus, regression-based data fusion can be considered a feasible and defensible approach for sample files with continuous variables that have a multivariate normal distribution.

3. Adding Random Residuals to Regression Estimates

The most essential innovation I developed for Kadane's and Rubin's methods is adding random residuals to the regression estimates. The methods did not work correctly without this innovation (Moriarity and Scheuren (2001a)).

My initial approach for this step (e.g., Moriarity and Scheuren (2001a)), which used subtraction of estimates created with information from both files, was not guaranteed to work correctly. It was not always feasible because it could yield a residual variance estimate that was negative. It became apparent (Moriarity and Scheuren (2003b)) that this was a crippling limitation when the residual variance being estimated was close to 0.

The method for generating residuals for RIEPS (Raessler (2002, p. 100) defines RIEPS as "regression imputation with random residual") discussed in Raessler (2002) used a different approach that had the advantage of always being feasible, but also had shortcomings (Moriarity and Scheuren (2004)).

D'Orazio, et al. (2006a) suggested using maximum likelihood estimation. Research I conducted in 2009 indicated that maximum likelihood estimation gave better results than my initial method, but there still were occurrences of negative residual variance estimates. Specifically, for the simulation described in Moriarity and Scheuren (2001a), my initial method gave negative residual variance estimates for the Y variable in File B for 143 out of the 1873 repetitions of the simulation; the maximum likelihood estimation method gave negative residual variance estimates for the Y variable in File B for 107 out of the 1873 repetitions of the simulation.

Kiesl and Raessler (2009) suggested an innovation of Raessler's RIEPS algorithm to address the shortcomings that were noted in Moriarity and Scheuren (2004). The essence of the innovation

was to iterate one part of the RIEPS algorithm to improve the statistical properties of the residual variance estimate. The original algorithm used what we referred to as the "primary" regression estimates (with no residual added) to produce "secondary" regression estimates; a sum of squares calculation involving the secondary regression estimates was the basis of the RIEPS residual variance estimate. The innovation iterates the primary/secondary process by taking the residuals estimated by the first set of secondary estimates, adding these residuals to the primary regression estimates, producing a new set of secondary regression estimates, generating an updated set of residuals, etc. Moriarity and Scheuren (2010) examined the RIEPS innovation within the simulation framework described in Moriarity and Scheuren (2001a). The examination gave clear evidence that the RIEPS innovation was superior to any previous method for generating residual variance estimates. Even in the 79 instances out of 1873 when the innovation did not converge, there was still a positive residual variance estimation provided (the original RIEPS result). When the innovation iterated one or more times and converged, the resulting residual variance estimates did not have the downward bias of the original RIEPS method. This innovation solved one of the two outstanding problems in data fusion.

4. The Set of Feasible Cov(Y,Z) Values

The remaining outstanding problem in data fusion is describing the set of feasible Cov(Y,Z) values when both Y and Z are multivariate. Without loss of generality, assume unit variances, so the covariance matrix is the correlation matrix.

Several things are known about the set of feasible values, independent of the dimensionality (e.g., Moriarity and Scheuren, 2010):

1. the set is convex; i.e., any linear combination of two feasible values is a feasible value.
2. the center of the set is at the conditional independence value.

When both Y and Z are univariate, the set of feasible values is known. If X is also univariate, the set of feasible values for Corr(Y,Z) is:

$$\text{Corr}(X,Y)*\text{Corr}(X,Z) \pm \text{sqrt}(1 - (\text{Corr}(X,Y)^2)) * \text{sqrt}(1 - (\text{Corr}(X,Z)^2))$$

The center of the interval, $\text{Corr}(X,Y)*\text{Corr}(X,Z)$, is the conditional independence value, i.e., the value of $\text{Corr}(Y,Z)$ when Y and Z are independent, given X.

Rodgers and DeVol (1982) generalized this result for multivariate X:

$$\text{Corr}(Y,X)*\text{Corr}(X,X)^{-1}*\text{Corr}(X,Z) \pm \text{sqrt}(1-(\text{Corr}(Y,X)*\text{Corr}(X,X)^{-1} * \text{Corr}(X,Y)) * \text{sqrt}(1 - (\text{Corr}(Z,X)*\text{Corr}(X,X)^{-1} * \text{Corr}(X,Z))$$

Kiesl and Raessler (2006) derived a closed-form result when one of (Y,Z) is univariate, the other multivariate: the interior of an ellipsoid.

At the present time, a closed-form result when both Y and Z are multivariate is not known to exist. The conjecture I made (2010 JSM proceedings) is false. However, given the Kiesl/Raessler 2006 result, it is reasonable to assert that the feasible set should be the interior of an ellipsoid. For example, a given correlation matrix with bivariate Y and Z could be relabeled to be univariate Y, trivariate Z; then, the Kiesl/Raessler 2006 result applies.

A result due to Schur (Schur's Identity) provides a starting point for constructing a description of the feasible set:

$$\det(\text{Corr}(X,Y,Z)) = \det(\text{Corr}(X,X)) * \det(\text{Corr}(Y,Z|X))$$

The determinant of a given correlation matrix is equal to the product of the determinants of the X correlation submatrix and the residual matrix from regressing Y,Z on X.

In data fusion, one may use File A, containing (X,Y), to estimate $\text{Corr}(X,Y)$, and use File B, containing (X,Z) to estimate $\text{Corr}(X,Z)$. If one then uses conditional independence to obtain a value of $\text{Corr}(Y,Z)$, the matrix $\text{Corr}(Y,Z|X)$ is block diagonal.

If, for example, X, Y, and Z are all bivariate, then the submatrix $\text{Corr}(Y,Z)$ and the residual matrix $\text{Corr}(Y,Z|X)$ are both 4 by 4 matrices.

Let the residual matrix $\text{Corr}(Y,Z|X)$ be of the form:

$$\begin{matrix} a & b & c & d \\ b & e & f & g \\ c & f & h & i \\ d & g & i & j \end{matrix}$$

At the vector of the conditional independence values, c, d, f, g are zero.

If one then seeks a value of c to make the determinant zero, while holding d, f, g at zero, and repeats the process for d, f, g, values are found that make $\det(\text{Corr}(X,Y,Z))=0$ (because of Schur's Identity).

For c, one obtains the equation:

$$0 = aehj - aei^2 - hjb^2 + (bi)^2 - ejc^2$$

Solving for c:

$$c = \pm \sqrt{1/ej} * \sqrt{aehj - aei^2 - hjb^2 + (bi)^2}$$

The expressions for d, f, and g are similar; they all include the term $\sqrt{aehj - aei^2 - hjb^2 + (bi)^2}$.

The general equation of an ellipsoid is a quadratic form, with symmetric positive definite matrix A:

$$(w-v)^T A (w-v) = 1$$

v is the vector of conditional independence values, i.e., the center of the ellipsoid.

The diagonal elements of A are the reciprocals of the squares of the values of c, d, f, g that make $\det(\text{Corr}(Y,Z|X))=0$.

One can then solve for the off-diagonal elements of A, one by one. For example, holding $\text{Corr}(Y_1,Z_2)$ and $\text{Corr}(Y_2,Z_2)$ at the conditional independence values reduces the ellipsoid equation to:

$$a_{11} (\text{Corr}(Y_1,Z_1) - [CI]\text{Corr}(Y_1,Z_1))^2 + 2a_{13} (\text{Corr}(Y_1,Z_1) - [CI]\text{Corr}(Y_1,Z_1)) (\text{Corr}(Y_2,Z_1) - [CI]\text{Corr}(Y_2,Z_1)) + a_{33} (\text{Corr}(Y_2,Z_1) - [CI]\text{Corr}(Y_2,Z_1))^2 = 1$$

where a_{11} and a_{33} are known, and the expression "[CI]" denotes the conditional independence value of what follows the expression.

Beginning at the conditional independence values of $\text{Corr}(Y_1, Z_1)$ and $\text{Corr}(Y_2, Z_1)$, search circles of increasing radii to arrive at a $(\text{Corr}(Y_1, Z_1), \text{Corr}(Y_2, Z_1))$ pair that gives a determinant of sigma (i.e., $\text{Corr}(X, Y, Z)$) that is very close to 0 (but still positive); then solve for a_{13} . This strategy exploits the hypothesized relationship between the feasible set and the non-singularity of sigma. As a pair $(\text{Corr}(Y_1, Z_1), \text{Corr}(Y_2, Z_1))$ is identified that gives a sigma that is still positive definite but very close to being singular, that same pair should be yielding a value of

$$a_{11} (\text{Corr}(Y_1, Z_1) - [\text{CI}]\text{Corr}(Y_1, Z_1))^2 + 2a_{13} (\text{Corr}(Y_1, Z_1) - [\text{CI}]\text{Corr}(Y_1, Z_1)) (\text{Corr}(Y_2, Z_1) - [\text{CI}]\text{Corr}(Y_2, Z_1)) + a_{33} (\text{Corr}(Y_2, Z_1) - [\text{CI}]\text{Corr}(Y_2, Z_1))^2$$

that is very close to, but less than, 1.

Consider a numeric example (sigma) with X, Y, Z bivariate:

1	0.5	0	0	0.25	0
0.5	1	0.75	0.5	0.5	0.75
0	0.75	1	0.75	0.375	0.75
0	0.5	0.75	1	0.25	0.5
0.25	0.5	0.375	0.25	1	0
0	0.75	0.75	0.5	0	1

The unobserved $\text{Corr}(Y, Z)$ entries are set equal to the conditional independence values (i.e., middle right: 0.375, 0.75, 0.25, 0.5).

$\det(\text{sigma}) = .0036621$, $\det(\text{Corr}(X, X)) = .75$, $\det(\text{Corr}(Y, Z|X)) = .0048828$;
 $\det(\text{Corr}(X, X)) * \det(\text{Corr}(Y, Z|X)) = .0036621$.

$\text{Corr}(Y, Z|X)$:

0.25	0.25	0 (c)	0 (d)
0.25	0.6666667	0 (f)	0 (g)
0	0	0.75	-0.375
0	0	-0.375	0.25

The values of c, d, f, g that lead to $\det=0$:

$c = \pm .1711633$, $d = \pm .0988212$, $f = \pm .2795085$, $g = \pm .1613743$.

The matrix A:

34.133333	51.200119	-12.8457	-18.32741
51.200119	102.4	-19.06903	-38.60716
-12.8457	-19.06903	12.8	19.200771
-18.32741	-38.60716	19.200771	38.4

To test the hypothesis, generate random (w-v) vectors: the first element is a fraction of the c value given above, the second element is a fraction of the d value given above, the third element is a fraction of the f value given above, and the fourth element is a fraction of the g value given above.

If $(w-v)^T A (w-v) < 1$ (interior of ellipsoid), add the vector elements to the appropriate entries of sigma, test to see if the matrix is still positive definite.

Result: approximately 500,000 random vectors out of one million generated were in the interior of the ellipsoid; all of them, after addition to elements of sigma, yielded a positive definite matrix.

A similar result was obtained for a sigma matrix with bivariate X and Y, trivariate Z; approximately 435,000 random vectors out of ten million generated, were in the interior of the ellipsoid; all of them, after addition to elements of sigma, yielded a positive definite matrix.

5. Discussion

The numerical results described above are not a proof, of course. They do provide evidence to support the hypothesis that the feasible set is the interior of an ellipsoid.

The ellipsoids determined above are not the maximally inclusive ellipsoids containing feasible values. While the diagonal elements of A are determined exactly, the off-diagonal elements are not. Pushing the search of circles of increasing radii to the point of driving the determinant of sigma to be very, very close to zero (while remaining positive) is not always feasible. This type of effort can result in creating a matrix A that is not positive definite. A more robust result appears to be obtained by not attempting to drive the determinant of sigma closer to zero by adding many more digits to the original coordinates obtained; however, this finding is based on limited research.

For the first numeric result, about 4.1% of the vectors outside of the ellipsoid yielded a positive definite matrix (i.e., false negatives). For the second numeric result, the false positive rate was approximately 0.15%; this ellipsoid is very close to the maximally inclusive shape.

6. Summary

An algorithm has been described above for determining the parameters of an ellipsoid that very closely approximates the set of feasible values when both Y and Z are multivariate. While this falls short of an analytic proof, it is a noteworthy advance, filling a long-standing gap in data fusion theory.

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